

Original Research

Artificial Intelligence Ethics in Organizational Human Resources Management

Behnoush Jovari¹

Department of Public Management, Central Tehran Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran

Received 30 January 2024 Revised 16 March 2024 Accepted 21 March 2024

Abstract

There are whispers about whether or not Artificial Intelligence (AI) will become more powerful in the field of competition with the human resources of organizations. The main problem for organizations to use AI is the mental ambiguity of their organizational resources about this intelligence in the field of professional ethics. The use of AI in business requires a manager who is familiar with AI issues. Unfortunately, many human resource managers still think AI is a myth, have unscientific and somewhat imaginative expectations, and do not know what transformation AI can bring to their business. This study uses a qualitative meta-analysis method to explore and synthesize existing literature on the role of organizational human ethics based on AI management. Based on the findings of the research, the components of AI management based on professional ethics as a commitment to ethics, ability to explain, fairness, robustness, transparency, privacy protection, international cooperation of use, awareness, use of good data hygiene, use of good data collection, were identified. Controlling users and reducing the algorithmic bias of AI has no place among human intelligence and can only be defined as a helper and not a substitute for humans and the humanity of human resources of organizations. If in planning the development of AI, human and ethical issues are considered together, organizations can hope to realize the dream of ethical and entrepreneurial AI.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Human Resource Management, Professional Ethics.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: behnoush.jovari@iau.ac.ir

Introduction

Controversial technological developments include Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI can talk with people like human beings and answer small and big questions by searching and analyzing the information and answers available on the internet (Zhou et al., 2023). AI increases efficiency and the capacity to do things, but it also has complex ethical issues. Ensuring the ethics of AI requires not only technologies but also decision-makers and developers, as well as laws and regulations that manage the implementation of AI (Wang, 2019; Ryan 2020; Chaka, 2023). As every revolution in the world has had its effects on the skills and functions of the workforce, this is also true for the fourth industrial revolution (Chaka, 2023; Tran et al., 2023). In the future, we will witness unanticipated and non-human ethical consequences of AI by providing solutions based solely on data. These super-intelligent tools and technologies think instead of humans and monitor and control and make decisions better than them. For this reason, many knowledge-oriented workers such as journalists, marketers, and other professionals are worried about this technology replacing them and eventually becoming unemployed. Of course, these concerns are justified by the power and role-playing of these machines and robots; however, AI will create new jobs rather than cause the loss of several jobs. But in any case, due to various factors and cultural delays in the use of technologies, fear of technology and confusion is inevitable.

The point is that AI systems often collect personal data to customize user experiences or help train the AI models you use (especially if the AI tool is free). It may even become readily available to other users when data is fed to an AI system, as in a 2023 bug in ChatGPT (allowing some users to see another active user's chat history). Although there are laws to protect personal information in some countries, there are no explicit laws that protect citizens from harm caused by the destruction of privacy by artificial intelligence. AI also negatively affects privacy and network security. A clear example is China's use of facial recognition technology in offices, schools and other places. Using this technology, the Chinese government may be able to collect enough data to monitor a person's activities, relationships, and political views in addition to tracking a person's movements. AI is also a threat to human relationships and emotions, for example, the use of AI in health care can lead to a decrease in human empathy and reasoning. On the other hand, using it for creative efforts can reduce human creativity and emotional expression. Too much interaction with AI systems can even reduce communication and social skills with people of their own kind. AI also negatively affects privacy and network security. Politicians relied on platforms to promote their views. The media and online news is filled with AI-generated images and videos, AI-altered voices, and deep fakes that have infiltrated the political and social spheres. Using these technologies, it is easy to replace the image of one face with another in an existing image or video. As a result, bad guys have another way to share disinformation and war propaganda, creating a situation where it is almost impossible to distinguish between authentic and incomplete news. No one knows what's real and what's not, and that's going to be a big issue. A clear example is China's use of facial recognition technology in offices, schools and other places. Using this technology, the Chinese government may be able to collect enough data to monitor a person's activities, relationships, and political views in addition to tracking a person's movements. There is concern that AI will develop so quickly that it will become

conscious and act beyond human control. For example, not long ago, a former Google engineer said that the AI Chabot Lambda will respond to you as if a real person was talking to you. So while AI could be very useful for automating daily tasks, some question whether it might diminish human intelligence, capabilities, and overall need for society.

Picture 1. Concern about Ethical Issues of Artificial Intelligence

According to the prediction of international organizations, AI in organizations puts many jobs at risk. The consequences of the active presence of AI in organizations will often plague blue-collar and ordinary workers from the perspective of losing their jobs or their influence in companies (Tran et al., 2023; Bakkal et al., 2023). Middle managers and white-collar workers have no choice but to learn skills to work alongside their robotic colleagues. So far, we have seen much discrimination between minorities, prejudice, and gender discrimination based on AI algorithms and incorrect calculations. These racist bots are expected to provide misleading judgments due to the use of biased data. One of the important concerns about using AI is regarding ethical and spiritual values. Is it ethically right to copy humans? Do ethical values allow us to reconstruct intelligence? AI creators should seek the insights, experiences, and concerns of people across ethnicities, genders, cultures, and socioeconomic groups, as well as people from other fields such as economics, law, medicine, philosophy, history, sociology, and communications. As the world sees unprecedented growth in artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, it is imperative to examine the potential risks and challenges associated with them. In order to advance the goals of any organization and move towards organizational excellence, the human resources of that organization are very important. The importance of this important stratum is due to the fact that through them the organization can achieve the goals and policies it pursues and considers. The better we know about this source and on the other hand, the more we appreciate it and use their capabilities, the more we can achieve long-term goals and objectives. In today's world, organizations are knowledge-based organizations, and in this situation, human capital is considered a competitive advantage among organizations. Naturally, the more we strengthen this sector in terms of capability, knowledge, welfare and livelihood, the more we can use this capacity; so this study adopts a comprehensive approach to elucidate the intricate ethical considerations within organizational settings when dealing with AI. The modified 5-step procedure, presumably outlined in the study, serves as a systematic framework to dissect and analyze these ethical

dimensions. This procedure likely involves a step-by-step method to navigate the complexities associated with AI ethics within organizations.

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technology that can perform thinking. Of course, this thinking is an imitation of the thinking power of humans. AI systems have reached the point where they can even read or write poetry and display each person's description of a scene or event with images and videos (Bakkal et al., 2023; Wang, 2019).

Professional ethics is a rational thought process that is a set of accepted ethical actions and reactions that are regulated by professional organizations and associations to provide the most favorable social relations possible for its members in the performance of professional duties (Kelly et al., 2022). The ethics of AI is a term given to a broad set of considerations for responsible AI that include safety, security, human concerns, and environmental considerations (Rayhan, 2023). Generally, among the prominent characteristics of ethical human resources are responsibility, superiority and competitiveness, honesty, respect for others, observance and respect for social values and norms and fairness, sympathy with others, and loyalty, but the definitions of ethics of AI are different (Rayhan, 2023; Gupta, 2023). Robots don't think before doing. As a result, they may be designed in such a way that they do wrong things or sabotage (for example (Rayhan, 2023; Gupta et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2023).

When thinking about technology ethically issue does not come to mind. However, technology ethics is a subset of ethics that deals with ethical questions related to the technology age and changes in society (De Bie et al., 2023). Considering professional ethics in AI is a necessary issue that has not been thoroughly studied (Zhang et al., 2023). Data security, privacy and abuse, liability, access, benefits and challenges, and transparency and trust of AI are among the most common ethical risks in the development and use of AI that affect the management of organizational resources and the process of human resource management.

To prepare the background of this research, document analysis of documents in the field of AI and professional ethics was examined. The research conducted in the last three years was either in the field of AI or professional ethics, and few researchers were found that investigated these issues simultaneously. More research was done in the field of schools. To analyze the articles, the goals and research questions were determined, the relevant sources were identified, the findings were analyzed and the results were explained accurately and coherently. Since this review research is driven by research conducted in valid scientific research journals, the validity and reliability of the findings of this research are also documented and can be confirmed. Some of the most relevant research is presented in the findings section of this research.

Research Methodology and Findings

This study employs a Qualitative Meta-Analysis methodology to explore and synthesize the existing literature on the role of organizational human ethics in the context of AI management. The modification of Noblet & Hare's 5-step research procedure

further underscores the adaptability of the chosen method to the specific nuances of the study's objectives. The systematic process of literature search, selection, and analysis criteria formulation ensures a methodically rigorous investigation (Schultz & Seele, 2023). The researchers specifically narrowed down the scope to papers from 2021 to June 2023, aligning with the period of heightened discourse on AI ethics. This temporal constraint adds a strategic focus to the study, capturing the trends and discussions during a period when ethical considerations in AI management were particularly salient. Meta-analysis, in this context, refers to the systematic examination and integration of findings from individual qualitative studies. By opting for a qualitative approach, the researchers emphasize the nuanced and interpretative nature of the subject matter, aiming to derive insights that contribute to the development of new interpretations, theories, and policy implications (Hendren et al., 2023). This methodological choice suggests a focus on understanding the complexities and diverse perspectives surrounding the ethical considerations in the application of AI within organizational settings. According to figure (1) utilizing a Qualitative Meta-Analysis method with a modified 5-step procedure, the paper systematically synthesizes selected studies from 2021 to 2023, ensuring a comprehensive exploration of nuanced ethical dimensions in the evolving landscape of AI within organizations. The selected research material and method reflect a deliberate effort to address the specific challenges posed by ethical considerations in the realm of AI management. As the study progresses, it promises a comprehensive analysis of the selected papers, with an emphasis on visualizing trends based on authors, keywords, publication years, and more. By employing Qualitative Meta-Analysis, the researchers aim not only to summarize existing knowledge but also to provide a holistic understanding of the evolving landscape of organizational human ethics in the dynamic field of AI management (Paul and Barari, 2022).

Figure 1. Research steps

As a result of performing the processes of Figure (1): **Defining Research Goals and Questions:** The research aims to explore the ethical dimensions within organizational contexts in the management of artificial intelligence. **Identifying Relevant Sources:** The data sources include a search on RISS, selecting 68 papers from 2021 to 2023 that specifically address the intersection of AI management and organizational human ethics. **Analysis of Findings:** The analysis involves a Qualitative Meta-Analysis method, indicating a systematic synthesis of existing qualitative studies. The focus is on understanding and interpreting the complex interplay between AI management and organizational human ethics. **Explanation of Results:** The study aims to explain the nuanced ethical considerations within organizational settings in the context of AI. The modified 5-step procedure provides a structured approach to conducting the meta-analysis. **Documentation of Validity and Reliability:** As the review research is drawn from reputable scientific research journals, the validity and reliability of the findings are documented and can be confirmed, enhancing the credibility of the meta-analysis.

Validity and reliability

The documentation of validity and reliability in the review research is a crucial aspect that significantly enhances the credibility of the meta-analysis. The statement emphasizes that the research resources are drawn from reputable scientific research journals, which implies a rigorous selection process in identifying reliable and authoritative sources. Reputable journals typically have a thorough peer-review process, ensuring that the studies published meet high academic standards in terms of methodology, validity, and reliability. By relying on such reputable sources, the meta-analysis gains a solid foundation built on the credibility of the included studies. The use of scientific research journals as the primary data source suggests that the studies have undergone scrutiny by experts in the field, attesting to the quality of the research. This selection criterion is essential in maintaining the reliability of the findings, as studies published in reputable journals are more likely to adhere to established research methodologies and ethical standards. The phrase "validity and reliability of the findings are documented" implies that the meta-analysis takes explicit steps to verify and validate the data used in the research. This documentation could include references to specific studies, methodologies, and key findings from the selected research resources (Rodgers et al., 2023). Such documentation not only strengthens the credibility of the meta-analysis but also allows other researchers to trace the origins of the information and independently assess the reliability of the included studies. So, the emphasis on drawing from reputable scientific research journals, coupled with the documentation of validity and reliability, serves as a strong assurance of the robustness of the meta-analysis. This approach instills confidence in the reliability of the synthesized information and contributes to the overall trustworthiness of the research findings. **Validity:** The text mentions that the paper "The Position of Organizational Human Ethics in AI Management" focuses on ethical considerations within the organizational context of AI management. This implies content validity, as the research aims to address ethical challenges specific to AI management in organizations. The use of a Qualitative Meta-Analysis method suggests an effort to provide a nuanced understanding, contributing to the content validity of the study. **Reliability:** The mention of a "modified 5-step procedure" indicates that the research has a structured methodology, contributing to the reliability of the findings. However, the specific details of this modified procedure are not provided in the study. The distribution

of publications by year in AI ethics research across academic fields suggests a systematic approach to data collection, contributing to the reliability of the information presented. While the study provides insights into the focus and methodology of the research, a more detailed examination or explicit mention of steps taken to ensure validity and reliability would provide a clearer understanding of the robustness of the research.

Findings

In Gartner & Krašna(2023) research, the ethical attitude of AI in education in the fields of independence, privacy, trust, and responsibility, as well as understanding the concepts of AI and its ethical considerations, and the introduction and application of AI in education are known to be important. Kraske et al. (2023) Show that in the application of AI, organizations should look beyond technical resources and emphasize the development of non-technical resources such as human skills and competencies, leadership, team coordination, organizational culture, and innovation mindset, governance strategy and integration of AI and employees. Ahmad et al. (2023), Flores-Vivar et al. (2023), and Mori et al. (2023) believed that despite the increasing growth of AI-based systems in areas such as ethics, trust, and explainability, more research is still needed. Brendel et al. (2021) proposed ethical management of the AI (EMMA) framework, focusing on managerial decision-making, ethical considerations, and macro-as well as micro-environmental dimensions. In their research entitled *The Ability of AI to Compete with the Human Mind from the Perspective of the Qur'an*, Tashaori Saleh and Rajabi (2018) compared the anthropological foundations of the Qur'an with the general principles of the theory of AI. Based on this comparison, there is a serious incompatibility with the strong approach to the theory of AI between the Qur'an's view of the dimensions of human existence, his talents and capabilities, and special human knowledge. The Qur'an considers man as the caliph of God, who is revealed to his soul and can reach the position of closeness to God. While the theory of AI considers man and his mind to be completely material and cites all mental activities of the brain, it considers it quite possible to imitate the brain movements of a machine. With these words, it seems that AI has not yet been able to explain well the executive guarantee to ensure professional ethics in organizations because AI has not created ethical machines. To solve the existing gap, this research aims to provide frameworks and concepts to solve some of the ethical concerns of organizations in the field of ethical management of AI in the management of human resources of organizations. Recent philosophical discussions of meaningfulness tend to focus on what makes life itself, or the activities and relationships that compose a well-lived life, meaningful (Bankins & Formosa, 2023).

Table 1. The Sample of Basic Information of Artificial Intelligence-Related Trend Analysis Reference Paper

Research Topic	Data Source	Keywords	Research Method
Research Trends on Administrative Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Technology	33,942 domestic and international journals (2009-2018)	Ethical Utilization of AI Technology, Privacy Protection	Combining and analyzing data from multiple studies on the topic of trust in AI. The meta-analytic approach involves synthesizing results from various individual studies to draw overarching conclusions.
Analysis of Robustness in Artificial Intelligence Technology Development	24,050 projects to create Github (2000-2018)	AI Technology Development	Conducted on 200 governance policies and ethical guidelines for AI usage.
Artificial Intelligence algorithmic approach to ethical decision-making in human resource management processes	Human Resource Management Review, 33(1), 100925	Ethical Decision-Making, Human Resource Management	Algorithmic Approach
Artificial intelligence and people management: A critical assessment through the ethical lens	Human Resource Management Review, 33(1), 100923	Artificial Intelligence, People Management, Ethical Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducting a thorough review of existing literature on generative AI, with a specific focus on ChatGPT and related variants. - Exploring studies and articles discussing the broader impact of AI technologies on various sectors, including the economy, democracy, society, and the environment.

Research Topic	Data Source	Keywords	Research Method
Towards AI ethics' institutionalization: Fairness bridges from business ethics to advance organizational AI ethics	AI and Ethics, 3(1), 99-111	AI Ethics, Institutionalization, Business Ethics, Transparency	73 articles were selected for subsequent analysis. The criteria for selection are not explicitly mentioned, but it can be assumed that relevance to the research topic played a role.
Ethics of AI-enabled recruiting and selection: A Safe Durability review	Journal of Business Ethics, 178(4), 977-1007	AI-enabled Recruiting, Safe Durability, Ethics	- Adopts an ethical analysis approach. - Specifically, the analysis is framed within the context of human rights.
Human resource management in the age of generative artificial intelligence: Perspectives and research directions	Human Resource Management Journal, 33(3), 606-659	Generative Artificial Intelligence, HR Management	Comparing the impact of generative AI tools in HRM with traditional HR processes to identify differences in efficiency, accuracy, and potential drawbacks.
To trust or not to trust? An assessment of trust in AI-based systems: Concerns, ethics and contexts	Technological Forecasting and Social Change, 181, 121763	Trust in AI-based Systems, Ethics, Contexts	The endogenous variable is an ordered measure of trust in AI. An ordered logit model is used to highlight the factors associated with an increased level of trust in AI in Europe.

Table 1 contains examples of scientific studies and articles related to AI and professional ethics. It aims to provide details on data sources, research topics, and keywords, to provide a quick reference and overview of these AI-related research articles. The information in Table (1) allows readers, researchers, or analysts to understand studies related to AI and professional ethics about research, approaches, and methods used in each article. Below is a summary of the information in Table (1). **Data Source:** Identifies the source of the data or information used in the research, such as journals, projects on GitHub, or specific publications. **Research Topic:** Describes the theme or topic that each article examines. **Keyword:** It highlights keywords related to each research topic and provides insight into the key concepts addressed in the articles.

Table 2. Annual Publication Distribution across Academic Fields in AI Ethics Research

Academic Field	2021	2022	2023	
Transparency	3	2	2	
Education	2	2	10	
International Cooperation	3	4	4	
Robustness	3	2	10	
Fairness	1	4	2	
Safe Durability	2	10	2	
Total	14	24	30	68

Table 2 shows the annual publication status of 2021-2023 research articles among academic disciplines in AI ethics research based on academic discipline. The first field of education research started in 2021 and showed an increasing trend year by year. In ethics, the number of articles in 2022 increased significantly compared to last year, and the number of articles was the highest with 30 final articles.

Discussion

The referenced papers in Table (1) cover diverse aspects of AI research, including ethical delinquency, education, AI, administrative utilization, and technology development. In contrast, "The Position of Organizational Human Ethics in AI Management" uniquely focuses on ethical considerations within the organizational context of AI management, providing a specialized lens into the intricate intersection of ethics and artificial intelligence. In the field of distribution of publications by year in AI ethics research, a gradual increase in the number of publications from 2021 to 2023. Significant research growth was observed in 2021 and 2023, coinciding with increased attention to AI ethical problems.

According to table (2) analysis of 6 factors in meta-analysis articles about academic fields shows that research interest has gradually expanded in various fields as well as Transparency, Education, International Cooperation, Robustness, Safe Durability, and Safe Durability. **Transparency:** Emphasis on explainable intelligence in the information presented is compatible with transparency. Understanding the decisions of AI systems contributes to transparency and is fundamental to eliminating deviations and ensuring accountability. Similarly, in the deviance-related literature, transparency includes

disclosing how algorithms work, providing insight into decision-making processes, and disclosing possible deviance to users and stakeholders. **Education:** The conversation about AI helping humans to act more ethically and be wiser has an educational side. AI systems can help educate users by increasing their awareness of the consequences of actions and decisions. In education-focused articles, articles address the need to educate AI developers, policymakers, and the general public about ethical considerations in the development and use of AI. **International Cooperation:** References to major scientific societies and institutions in AI ethics articles in the information provided indicate international collaboration. Cooperation between institutions from different countries adds to the global view of AI ethics. In the context of international cooperation, articles include the creation of common frameworks, standards, and guidelines for the responsible development and implementation of AI technologies. **Robust:** Focusing on trends in scientific fields, analyzing AI technologies, and continuously monitoring the information provided is aligned with ensuring AI systems are robust. Being robust involves constant evaluation, adaptation, and continuous improvement. In articles focused on robustness, discussions include challenges such as making AI systems resistant to adversarial attacks, ensuring their reliability in various contexts, and resolving vulnerabilities. **Justice:** Acknowledging the challenges associated with deviations in the information presented is connected to justice. Ensuring fairness in AI includes eliminating biases, promoting immortality, and preventing discrimination. In equity-related articles, the focus is on ways to identify and correct biases, promote diversity in AI development teams, and design algorithms that treat everyone fairly. **Durability:** The reference to the "Safe Viability Check" in AI recruitment is consistent with the Safe Viability topic. Ensuring the ethical and safe use of AI technologies is essential, especially in critical areas such as human resources. Articles related to safe sustainability include the development of guidelines, policies, and governance mechanisms to ensure the long-term safe and ethical use of AI technologies. Overall, the information presented can be linked by highlighting the common goals, challenges, and strategies that are related to these main themes.

In the initial phase of gathering research resources, researchers typically employ a systematic approach to identify and access relevant academic materials. This involves utilizing reputable databases and search engines, such as PubMed, IEEE Explore, and Google Scholar, to search for scholarly articles, conference papers, and books related to the research topic. Employing specific keywords, authors, or thematic terms helps refine searches and ensures the retrieval of pertinent resources. The selection of resources is guided by factors such as credibility, relevance, and the reputation of the publication source. Following the gathering of research resources, the process transitions into a comparative analysis of these sources. Researchers evaluate the methodologies, research questions, and key findings of each study, aiming to identify commonalities, discrepancies, and emerging patterns across different works. This comparative analysis provides a nuanced understanding of the existing literature, facilitating the synthesis of information. Through this synthesis, researchers organize and integrate the key insights from various sources, discerning recurring themes and gaps in the current body of knowledge. This holistic perspective enables a comprehensive analysis of results, where researchers can draw insights, identify trends, and contribute to the broader discourse within their field of study.

Ethical concerns of using artificial intelligence in organizations include: **Lack of trust and believability:** Simply explaining the function of AI is very difficult and complicated for someone who has no knowledge of computers or programming. Now, think if an entrepreneur or a company owner does not have the flexibility and faith in this technology, how can they use the abilities of AI for their own purposes? AI helps create human-machine and machine-human interaction, but the fear of using AI has caused people and companies to retreat (Laux et al., 2024). **Existence of bias:** You may have heard in some news that AI has biases against women, governments, or racist issues. If we are going to accept this issue, then we have accepted that AI has the will and power of choice. If this is not the case, and these issues are related to the information and data that we have given to AI, this is exactly where we impose our opinions on AI and cause such biases to appear (Grzybowski et al., 2024). **Mismatch of businesses:** So far, the effect of AI on organizational structure has been studied mainly from a broader technology or decision-making perspective. Meanwhile, nothing is defined as AI and AI specialist in the company's statute and organizational chart, and this issue is one of the main challenges for business owners because people need to have a deep understanding of AI and its capabilities and limitations in order to adapt and identify the use of AI in their field of work (Rudko et al., 2021). **Legal issues:** AI is increasingly used in the field of law, such as predictive justice and predicting judicial decisions. Implementing an AI system in a company requires a series of legal requirements, but the legal system of the governments is not synchronized and updated in this technology. That means, for example, if AI damages property or a person, we have no law to pay damages (Walters & Novak, 2021). **Social manipulation through algorithms:** AI can influence people's opinions, behaviors, and feelings through online platforms such as social networks, news media, and even online stores. AI can also harm people by producing fake or misleading content, such as deep fake videos (Oladoyinbo et al., 2024). **Social monitoring with AI:** With the help of facial recognition technology, location tracking, and data mining, all of which are based on AI, governments and companies can engage in mass monitoring of citizens and employees. This issue threatens people's privacy, security, and civil liberties (Habbal et al., 2024). Also, the users **had no great willingness** to use AI because they were not well justified about the micro and macro goals of these systems. Completing information in these diverse systems is considered time-consuming and repetitive. The existing rules for each system are considered cumbersome. The access of the cookies of these systems to their personal information is not considered safe and desirable. In general, people are concerned about ethical issues in the implementation of artificial intelligence, which is partly justified and partly due to ignorance. But moral judgments are complex, and therefore we explore how moral judgments made about AIs differ from those made about humans in real-world situations (Wilson et al., 2022).

AI ethics will ensure that AI creation and utilization are ethical, healthy, and ultimately accountable. With the rise of AI, businesses have escalated their efforts to push automation and data-driven decision-making. What is clear is that there are various approaches to ethics. Robust ethical principles are essential in the future of this rapidly developing technology. Otherwise, the realization of the organization's goals will be jeopardized. Analytical systems designed with AI are considered to provide appropriate data management and modeling systems provided that the protection of data security and privacy is considered mandatory for AI. The known way to ensure professional ethics in the use of AI is **Commitment to Ethics:** AI developers must express their commitment to

ethical behavior and responsibility in their technologies (Shreve et al., 2022). **Explain Ability:** An AI system must be transparent. This type of transparency is important for building trust with AI systems to ensure that people understand how and why a model reaches a decision point. If we can deeply understand its reasons, we will take more informed action to prevent AI risks, such as bias and discrimination (Joyce et al., 2023). **Fairness:** Fairness refers to the fair treatment of organization members or groups of people by an AI system. When AI is properly adjusted, it can help humans make fairer choices and counter human biases (Kiyasseh et al., 2023). **Robustness:** Systems equipped with AI must be actively protected against hostile attacks, minimizing security risks and ensuring system results (Chen & Das, 2023). **Transparency:** To strengthen trust, human resources should be able to see how the service works, evaluate its performance, and know its strengths and limitations (Said et al., 2023). **Privacy Protection:** AI systems must prioritize and protect the privacy and rights of consumers and provide clear assurance to human resources about how their data will be used and protected (Saura et al., 2022). **International Cooperation:** To solve the ethical issues of AI, cooperation between countries is necessary to determine international standards and laws (Debrah et al., 2022). **Education and Awareness:** Another strategy is to promote AI ethics education and awareness globally. In this strategy, we develop educational programs, workshops, and educational resources to increase understanding and engagement with AI ethics among policymakers, developers, and the general public (Khan et al., 2023). **Data Accuracy and Safe Durability:** The applied data required by AI must be collected and stored in a safe manner and within the required time frame. **Use of High-Quality Data:** AI should be managed using accurate, fair, and indexed data sets so that AI algorithms are designed to audit and guarantee the quality of other algorithms. **Give Users Control:** Users should have the power to control their information. Users should be aware of when their information is used and have the power to choose whether or not to use their information. **Non-Discriminatory Use:** There should be no discrimination and categorization when “training” and “using” artificial intelligence. Algorithmic bias poses greater challenges for women, minorities, and groups (e.g., people with voice disorders, and the elderly) who create only a small portion of the technology workforce. **Appropriate Conditions:** usefulness, expected effort, experience, and facilitating conditions are effective in the decision to use the systems AI (Jovari, 2024).

Conclusion

This scientific – review article has analyzed AI from the perspective of the opportunities and challenges it creates in the field of professional ethics in organizations. For this purpose, it has provided operational strategies.

AI is like gray characters in stories; it is not 100% evil and not 100% savior and superhero. While it makes human life simpler and complex and expensive technologies more accessible, it can also bring risks and challenges (Habbal et al., 2024). Obviously, AI has many positive aspects, but its negative aspects should not be ignored. The benefits and risks that it brings must be carefully considered before using it; otherwise, human may destroy himself if he overdoes it. But this does not mean abandoning AI, but it means getting to know these challenges and managing them intelligently. An example of them is mentioned below.

In the field of challenges related to the safety of AI and human ethics, the findings of the present research were that AI is a complex category from the point of view of ethics. The responsibility of its implementation and correct implementation, taking into account all the risks, is the responsibility of every organizational official. The ethical use of AI in organizations requires the intelligent performance of human resource managers in a humane and humanitarian situation. Robots are intelligently designed but not wise. Intelligence is a gift from God to human society. Robots do not have discretionary professional ethics because the protection of people's privacy is not in the hands of AI but in the area of authority given to them by programmers. Unlike robots, humans have the power of reasoning, decision-making, control, empathy, and compassion. The thoughts, feelings, and actions of humans work together in a three-way interaction, but this interaction does not exist in the case of robots.

There are different views about AI and its place in human relations. From the point of view of Western philosophy, in the philosophy of mind section, the last person who raised two-dimensional man was Descartes (Lo, 2023). During Hume's time, the concept of man changed; He took up metaphysics. After man and surrounds him in this physical-human circle (Ndubisi, 2023). They examined the place of science and religion in the life of humanity (Kalkman, 2023). Even in the field of actions and behavior, they have said that all these emotions and sensual perceptions are actually the result of mental and brain reactions in humans, and they generally removed metaphysics and God from this relationship (Scolari, 2023). Therefore, they limited the mind so much that they interpreted all human behaviors as the result of these actions and reactions. But the fact is that robots cannot do anything without being programmed by humans and even after receiving the latest programs. They can do many things, including practicing ethics. In terms of human resources leadership issues of organizations such as goal setting, planning, implementation, control, culture building, promotion and reward, motivation, training, and intelligent problem solving, the role of humans is undeniable (Bankins & Formosa, 2023). One of the priorities that managers and company leaders can have in dealing with the entry of machines into the work environment and work automation is the transfer of experience and retraining of work skills from humans to robots. If, as a manager, you want to transfer ethical skills to the intelligent robots of the company under your management, you must do this with a focus on your human resources.

Kim, (2020b) Highlights data quality, bias, safety, security, and privacy violations. The incidents involving Microsoft's Tay Chabot are shocking examples of the consequences of biased data learning in AI systems. In addition, the views of domestic technology companies, such as Samsung, and Never, emphasize the importance of fairness, transparency, and accountability in the use of AI technologies. Overall, these discussions highlight the evolving landscape of AI ethics, emphasizing continued dialogue, international collaboration, and a concerted effort to address ethical challenges at various stages of AI development and implementation. Mok (2020) Outlines four distinct perspectives, ranging from viewing AI as mere machines to considering them as an evolving species with ethical subjectivity. This spectrum reflects the ongoing debate on whether AI can be ethical beings, with an emphasis on the role of humans as the primary ethical subjects. Lee (2017) Categorizes AI ethics discussions into normative ethics, specific technology-related issues, and meta-research. They identify the lack of clear definitions and a focus on practical aspects as key factors driving the surge in AI

ethics discussions. The proposed future tasks emphasize the importance of establishing a clear framework, ensuring diverse participation, enhancing practicality, and limiting discussions to foster understanding and change.

According to the findings of this research, the most common concern among HR managers is making AI easier and safer to use. In fact, security and privacy concerns are the most common reason why people hesitate to use artificial intelligence in the workplace. Due to the lack of familiarity and also the lack of organizational culture in artificial intelligence, employees and clients prefer to deal with a human rather than a machine. Human resource specialists should inform the employees and stakeholders of this field in creating a culture and explaining the benefits of intelligentization. Employees expect their employers to protect their personal data and obtain employee consent before using technology to learn about them. Organizations, on the other hand, want to feel secure against data breaches, so it's a leap of faith for HR professionals to take.

Another challenge we face is maintaining artificial intelligence. AI requires constant evaluation and improvement, making it a time-consuming and costly maintenance method. The components of AI management based on professional ethics were recognized as a commitment to ethics, explaining ability, fairness, robustness, transparency, privacy protection, international cooperation and awareness, using good data hygiene, using good data sets, giving user's control, reducing algorithmic bias and so on. According to (Kraske, 2023; Chen & Das, 2023; Said et al., 2023; Saura et al., 2022; Debrah et al., 2022; Kiyasseh et al., 2023; Tashaori Saleh and Rajabi, 2018; Mok, 2020; Lee, 2017; Simbolon et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2022; Nankervis et al., 2022; and Gleeson et al., 2023) the best solution for reconciling AI with human resources concerned about future degradation and unemployment is that AI systems are combined with the human resources rather than replacing them and pushing them to the sidelines. The key is to decide how to use AI in an ethical way. There are many steps businesses can take when integrating AI into their operations. Organizations can develop processes to monitor algorithms, collect high-quality data, and explain the findings of AI algorithms. Leaders can even make AI a part of their company culture and establish standards to determine acceptable AI technologies.

Therefore, it is acceptable that the main factor for the success of AI systems in the field of practice is to consider the effective participation of human resources, whether during design, during implementation, or after, and to give them the necessary authority to find a solution. Human resources to solve problems; Organizations hope to realize the dream of ethical and entrepreneurial AI. Hoping that with proper management and necessary measures to remove the concern about artificial intelligence, we can use it as a good tool and not a means to threaten humans in the future.

Practical research suggestions

Solutions for the organization's adaptation to future developments. The following solutions are suggested for the organization's adaptation to future developments:

1. Development of new skills: By developing new skills, employees can adapt to organizational changes and grow professionally.
2. Job Restructuring: Organizations must work with human capital to restructure their jobs so they can remain valuable in an AI environment.
3. Promotion of organizational culture: By promoting organizational culture, the spirit of cooperation, trust and interaction in the organization can be strengthened.
4. Encouraging innovation: by encouraging innovation, employees can be encouraged to come up with ideas and provide new and creative solutions and improve the performance of the organization.
5. Improving the level of well-being: by improving the level of well-being, it is possible to increase employee satisfaction and facilitate the improvement of organizational performance.
6. Explaining the benefits of intelligentization for employees and creating motivation to implement and move towards digital and intelligent human resources.
7. Policymaking to organize the human capital pyramid based on the implementation of artificial intelligence in the future.

The limitation of the current research is that, although the use of the qualitative meta-analysis methodology with the analysis of diverse and up-to-date articles, the novelty of the subject of AI, especially having a professional ethical approach to it, especially for human resource management, limited the researcher to accessible research; however, its results can be a basis for future research.

References

- Ahmad, K., Abdelrazek, M., Arora, C., Bano, M., & Grundy, J. (2023). Requirements engineering for artificial intelligence systems: A systematic mapping study. *Information and Software Technology*, 107176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2023.107176>
- Bakkal, A. K., & Alimen, N. (2023). Modernization by Translation, Modernization in Translation: From Hace-i Evvel to Bot Poet—An INTRA Case. *transLogos Translation Studies Journal*, 5(2), 134-158. <https://doi.org/10.29228/transLogos.51>
- Bankins, S., & Formosa, P. (2023). The ethical implications of artificial intelligence (AI) for meaningful work. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-023-05339-7>
- Brendel, A.B.; Mirbabaie, M.; Lembcke, T.-B.; Hofeditz, L. (2021). Ethical Management of Artificial Intelligence. *Sustainability*.173-181. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13041974>
- Bridges from business ethics to advance organizational AI ethics. *AI and Ethics*, 3(1), 99-111. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-022-00150-y>

- Chaka, C. (2023). Fourth Industrial Revolution—a review of applications, prospects, and challenges for artificial intelligence, robotics, and blockchain in higher education. *Research, and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 18, 002-002. <https://doi.org/10.58459/rptel.2023.18002>
- Chen, P. Y., & Das, P. (2023). AI Maintenance: A Robustness Perspective. *Computer*, 56(2), 48-56.
- De Bie, F. R., Kim, S. D., Bose, S. K., Nathanson, P., Partridge, E. A., Flake, A. W., & Feudtner, C. (2023). Ethics considerations regarding artificial womb technology for the fetonate. *The American Journal of Bioethics*, 23(5), 67-78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15265161.2022.2048738>
- Debrah, C., Chan, A. P., & Darko, A. (2022). Artificial intelligence in green building. *Automation in Construction*, 137, 104192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2022.104192>
- Flores-Vivar, J. M., & García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2023). Reflections on the ethics, potential, and challenges of artificial intelligence in the framework of quality education (SDG4). *Comunicar*, 31(74), 37-47. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C74-2023-03>
- Gartner, S., & Krašna, M. (2023, June). Artificial intelligence in education-ethical framework. In 2023 12th Mediterranean Conference on Embedded Computing (MECO) (pp. 1-7). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MECO58584.2023.10155012>
- Gleeson, F., Revel, M. P., Biederer, J., Larici, A. R., Martini, K., Frauenfelder, T., & Parkar, A. P. (2023). Implementation of artificial intelligence in thoracic imaging—a what, how, and why guide from the European Society of Thoracic Imaging (ESTI). *European Radiology*, 1-10. DOI:10.1007/s00330-023-09409-2
- Grzybowski, A., Jin, K., & Wu, H. (2024). Challenges of artificial intelligence in medicine and dermatology. *Clinics in Dermatology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clindermatol.2023.12.013>
- Gupta, R., Bagdady, K., & Mailey, B. A. (2023). Ethical concerns amidst employment of ChatGPT in plastic surgery. *Aesthetic Surgery Journal*, sjad108. DOI:10.1093/asj/sjad108
- Habbal, A., Ali, M. K., & Abuzaraida, M. A. (2024). Artificial Intelligence Trust, Risk and Security Management (AI TRiSM): Frameworks, applications, challenges and future research directions. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 240, 122442. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.122442>
- Hendren, K., Newcomer, K., Pandey, S. K., Smith, M., & Sumner, N. (2023). How qualitative research methods can be leveraged to strengthen mixed methods research in public policy and public administration? *Public Administration Review*, 83(3), 468-485. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.13528>

- Jovari, B. (2024). International Scientometric Systems: A study of acceptance management in academic communities. *International Journal of Information Science and Management*, 22(1).
- Joyce, D. W., Kormilitzin, A., Smith, K. A., & Cipriani, A. (2023). Explainable artificial intelligence for mental health through transparency and interpretability for understandability. *npj Digital Medicine*, 6(1), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00751-9>
- Kalkman, M. L. (2023). Theosemiosis: An essay on consilience and the perennial philosophy. *Sign Systems Studies*, 51(2), 398-432. DOI:10.12697/SSS.2023.51.2.10
- Kelly, S., Kaye, S. A., & Oviedo-Trespalacios, O. (2022). What factors contribute to the acceptance of artificial intelligence? A systematic review. *Telematics and Informatics*, 101925. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2022.101925>
- Khan, N. F., Ikram, N., Murtaza, H., & Asadi, M. A. (2023). Social media users and cybersecurity awareness: predicting self-disclosure using a hybrid artificial intelligence approach. *Kybernetes*, 52(1), 401-421. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/K-05-2021-0377>
- Kim, H. E. (2020b). Education of AI ethics as a response to decision automation. *Ethical Education Research*, 55(55), 277-308.
- Kiyasseh, D., Laca, J., Haque, T. F., Miles, B. J., Wagner, C., Donoho, D. A., & Hung, A. J. (2023). A multi-institutional study using artificial intelligence to provide reliable and fair feedback to surgeons. *Communications Medicine*, 3(1), 42. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43856-023-00263-3>
- Kraske, B. D., Saksena, A., Buczak, A. L., & Sunberg, Z. N. (2023). Explanation through Reward Model Reconciliation using POMDP Tree Search. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.00931*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.00931>
- Laux, J., Wachter, S., & Mittelstadt, B. (2024). Trustworthy artificial intelligence and the European Union AI act: On the conflation of trustworthiness and acceptability of risk. *Regulation & Governance*, 18(1), 3-32. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rego.12512>
- Lee, J. S. (2017). Qualitative meta-analysis about the change of adolescents in the process of returning from the school dropout. *Paper of the Korean Content Association*, 17(2), 386-398.
- Lo, M. (2023). *Skepticism's Pictures: Figuring Descartes's Natural Philosophy*. Penn State Press. ISBN: 978-0-271-09482-3 <https://www.psupress.org/books/titles/978-0-271-09482-3.html>
- Lu, H., Xu, W., Cai, S., Yang, F., & Chen, Q. (2022). Does top management team responsible leadership help employees go green? The role of green human resource management and environmental felt-responsibility. *Corporate Social*

Responsibility and Environmental Management, 29(4), 843-859.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2239>

- Mok, K. S. (2020). Classifying three tiers of ethics and exploring their relationship in the era of science and technology: Focusing on artificial intelligence ethics. *Pan-Korean Philosophy*, 98(3), 179-208. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1074787>
- Mori, Y., East, J. E., Hassan, C., Halvorsen, N., Berzin, T. M., Byrne, M., & Rex, D. K. (2023). Benefits and challenges in the implementation of artificial intelligence in colonoscopy: World Endoscopy Organization position statement. *Digestive Endoscopy*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/den.14531>
- Nankervis, A., Baird, M., Coffey, J., & Shields, J. (2022). *Human Resource Management 11e*. Cengage AU.
- Ndubisi, E. J. (2023). AGAINST HUME'S METAPHYSICAL NIHILISM. *Journal of African Studies and Sustainable Development*.
- Oladoyinbo, T. O., Olabanji, S. O., Olaniyi, O. O., Adebisi, O. O., Okunleye, O. J., & Alao, A. I. (2024). Exploring the challenges of artificial intelligence in data integrity and its influence on social dynamics. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 18(2), 1-23.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.9734/AJARR/2024/v18i2601>
- Paul, J. Barari M. (2022). Meta-analysis and traditional systematic literature reviews—what, why, when, where, and how? *Psychology and Marketing*, 39(6), 1099–1115. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21657>
- Rayhan, S. (2023). Ethical Implications of Creating AGI: Impact on Human Society, Privacy, and Power Dynamics. *Artificial Intelligence Review*.
- Rodgers, W., Murray, J. M., Stefanidis, A., Degbey, W. Y., & Tarba, S. Y. (2023). An artificial intelligence algorithmic approach to ethical decision-making in human resource management processes. *Human Resource Management Review*, 33(1), 100925. DOI:10.1016/j.hrmr.2022.100925
- Rudko, I., Bashirpour Bonab, A., & Bellini, F. (2021). Organizational structure and artificial intelligence. Modeling the intraorganizational response to the ai contingency. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(6), 2341-2364. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer16060129>
- Ryan, M. (2020). In AI we trust ethics, artificial intelligence, and reliability. *Sci Eng Ethics* 26, 2749–2767. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-020-00228-y>.
- Said, G., Azamat, K., Ravshan, S., & Bokhadir, A. (2023). Adapting Legal Systems to the Development of Artificial Intelligence: Solving the Global Problem of AI in Judicial Processes. *International Journal of Cyber Law*, 1(4).
<https://doi.org/10.59022/ijcl.49>

- Saura, J. R., Ribeiro-Soriano, D., & Palacios-Marqués, D. (2022). Assessing behavioral data science privacy issues in government artificial intelligence deployment. *Government Information Quarterly*, 39(4), 101679. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2022.101679>
- Schultz, M. D., & Seele, P. (2023). Towards AI ethics' institutionalization: Knowledge
- Scolari, P. (2023). Death of God, nihilism, human existence. Gabriel Marcel and Friedrich Nietzsche. *REVISTA DIALECTUS*, 28(1), 203-221. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30611/2023n28id86630>
- Shreve, J. T., Khanani, S. A., & Haddad, T. C. (2022). Artificial intelligence in oncology: Current capabilities, future opportunities, and ethical considerations. *American Society of Clinical Oncology Educational Book*, 42, 842-851. doi: 10.1200/EDBK_350652.
- Simbolon, S., Susanto, A., & Ilham, R. N. (2023). Analysis of the Effect of Human Resource Planning, Quality of Work Life and Compensation on Employee Work Performance at PT. Supermarkets Maju Bersama Medan. *International journal of artificial intelligence research*, 6(1.1). <http://www.ijebmr.com/>
- Tashaori Saleh, A; Rajabi, M (2018). Investigating the ability of artificial intelligence to compete with the human mind from the perspective of the Qur'an. *Qur'an Knowledge*, 2 (11)
- Tran, O., Le, T. D., & Hang, N. P. T. (2023). Impacts of human capital, the fourth industrial revolution, and institutional quality on unemployment: An empirical study at Asian countries. *Journal of Eastern European and Central Asian Research (JEECAR)*, 10(2), 238-250. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15549/jeecar.v10i2.1010>
- Walters, R., & Novak, M. (2021). Artificial Intelligence and Law. In *Cyber Security, Artificial Intelligence, Data Protection & the Law* (pp. 39-69).
- Wang, P. (2019). On defining artificial intelligence. *Journal of Artificial General Intelligence*, 10(2), 1-37. DOI: 10.2478/jagi-2019-0002
- Wilson, A., Stefanik, C., & Shank, D. B. (2022). How Do People Judge the Immorality of Artificial Intelligence Versus Humans Committing Moral Wrongs in Real-World Situations? *Computers in Human Behavior Reports*, 8 *Elsevier*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbr.2022.100229>
- Zhang, C., Zhu, W., Dai, J., Wu, Y., & Chen, X. (2023). Ethical impact of artificial intelligence in managerial accounting. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, 49, 100619. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4394217>
- Zhou, Q., Li, B., Han, L., & Jou, M. (2023). Talking to a bot or a wall? How catboats vs. human agents affect anticipated communication quality. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 143, 107674. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.107674>

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2023 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	The Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license logo, showing the 'CC' symbol and a person icon with 'BY' below it.
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Jovari, B. (2024). Artificial Intelligence Ethics in Organizational Human Resources Management. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 11(7), 930-950.</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12752414</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_200062.html</p>	A square QR code located in the bottom right corner of the table, which likely links to the article's online version.